

HYPIEND

Understanding and preventing the impact of endocrine disruptors on the hypothalamus-pituitary axis in sensitive populations

The **HYPIEND** project investigates the effects of multiple **Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals (EDCs)** exposure on the function and epigenetic programming of the **hypothalamus-pituitary (HP)** axis. It is one of the first projects to study this using a **multidisciplinary approach**.

The main goal is to **delineate interventional strategies** for minimizing its exposure and consequences on the neuroendocrine system during **the perinatal and pre-pubertal stages**.

Multidisciplinary approach

Computational data analysis to identify coexposure patterns

Laboratory studies on effects of EDCs exposure in HP axis

Intervention studies in pregnancy, breastfeeding and childhood

Start-end date

January 2024 - December 2028

Duration

60 months

Budget

€ 6,694,438.25, 100% funded by the European Commission

HYPIEND project will conduct two lifestyle intervention studies

1 In **pregnant and breastfeeding women**, and their **offspring** up to 18 months

Spain, Belgium and Poland

810 pregnant women and their infants

2 In **children** aged 6-8 years old, **parents**, and **schools**

Spain and Belgium

700 prepubertal 6-8 children and their parents

Where can EDCs be found?

- Pesticides
- Clothing, furniture, paints, electronics
- Food and drinking
- Food contact materials
- Plastics and plasticizers
- Personal care products
- Household cleaning products
- Children products (e.g. toys)
- Industrial chemicals

The studies will use...

Behavioural change app

Educational workshops

School educational programme

eurecat

Radoud Universiteit

IGTP

sciensano

KU LEUVEN

UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA

CENTRE OF POSTGRADUATE MEDICAL EDUCATION

ProtoQSAR

Computational toxicology: fast, economical and ethical

enco

IIS La Fe

LIÈGE université

UNIVERSITÉ DE GENÈVE

KING'S COLLEGE LONDON

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